

Sustainability Assessment systematic review into Non-destructive inspection technologies.

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ABSTRACT

Both sustainability assessment (SA) and non-destructive inspection (NDI) have been increasingly developed in the last two decades. SA is a cross-cutting concept that seeks to evaluate the impacts of three pillars: environmental, economic and social. In the field of NDI, which includes technologies aimed at evaluating critical product parameters throughout the manufacturing process and product life cycle to minimize defects and waste, the integration of these two concepts is essential for comprehensive evaluation and decision making. This review addresses two fundamental research questions using a systematic approach based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). First, what is the state of the practice in assessing the sustainability of these technologies? Second, which methodologies/ tools are used to analyze the environmental, economic, and social impacts of their implementation? Findings indicate that while sustainability is being addressed, performance often lacks depth, particularly in analyzing potential linkages between the pillars. To narrow this gap, the review was refined and conducted twice to broaden its scope, resulting in the development of a novel framework that promotes the integration of methodologies/ tools such as life cycle assessment, environmental life cycle costing, and social impact assessment into NDI practice. Such integration promises a more holistic application of sustainability principles, thereby facilitating their effective incorporation into the analysis of future NDI projects.

KEYWORDS

Non-destructive inspection, Life cycle assessment, Life cycle costing, Social Life Cycle Assessment, Sustainability assessment.

INTRODUCTION

Over the past two decades, the concepts of "sustainability" and "sustainable" have experienced exponential growth in academic literature. This surge, evidenced by a 17% average annual increase in published articles, reflects a mounting global awareness and concern regarding the responsible use of resources, all framed within the guiding ideology of sustainable development. The origins of this ideology can be traced back to 1987, when the World Commission on Environment and Development (WCED) introduced a foundational principle: "meeting the needs of the present without compromising the ability of future generations to meet their own needs" [1]. This principle has since become the cornerstone of sustainability discourse, profoundly shaping both theoretical frameworks and practical applications across various disciplines.

Building on this foundational principle, the concept of "sustainability assessment" (SA) has emerged. This methodology, which integrates approaches that both quantify and qualify sustainability, has led to the creation of various frameworks specifically tailored to the contexts in which they are deployed [2]. Over time, the concept of sustainability assessment has grown more nuanced and comprehensive, reflecting an increasingly sophisticated understanding of sustainability's complexities. Essentially, sustainability assessment involves any process that directs decision-making towards more sustainable outcomes. [3] This integration is in line with the growing trend of embedding sustainable practices across diverse fields and industries, a movement that is highlighted by an average annual growth rate of 18% in sustainability approaches over the past two decades.

In parallel, the field of Non-Destructive Inspection (NDI) has also seen significant advancements, driven by the need for efficient and reliable methods to evaluate critical product parameters throughout the manufacturing process and product life cycle. NDI technologies have become indispensable in industries that demand high standards of quality and safety, offering methods to detect defects and irregularities without causing damage to the components being inspected [4]. The literature also shows its exponential growth, with an average annual growth rate of 11%. These technologies include Ultrasonic testing, Acoustic emission Radiographic techniques Electromagnetic techniques Thermographic techniques and advanced digital twins, among others [5].

To review how SA has been implemented into NDI, this paper addresses two fundamental research questions using a systematic review based on the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA). First, what is the current state of practice in assessing the sustainability of NDI technologies? Second, which methodologies and tools are used to analyze the environmental, economic, and social impacts of their implementation?

Despite the growing body of literature on sustainability assessments, current practices in NDI technologies still show significant gaps, particularly in understanding the interconnections between the environmental, economic, and social pillars of sustainability. It was found that these approaches often focus too narrowly on individual aspects, such as environmental impact, without fully considering how these factors interact with economic viability and social consequences. This fragmented view risks incomplete or misleading assessments, which can undermine decision-making and policy development [6].

This study aims to bridge the gap by providing a comprehensive overview of SA in NDI. The main objectives of this study are:

- Explore the contribution of SA to NDI.
- Describe the technical principles and application of SA in different NDI technologies.
- Define a tailored framework for SA into NDI.

The structure of this paper is divided into six main sections. Following the introduction, the method section examines SA in the context of NDI. Then, framework section develops the second PRISMA report. The Results section examines the insights to construction an integrating approach, and the Discussion section explores the challenges and opportunities inherent in this framework. Finally, the Conclusion section synthesises the main results of the study.

METHOD

The preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA), a methodological framework designed to enhance the transparency and completeness of reporting in systematic reviews, was employed to ensure a rigorous selection process. For the initial search of relevant studies, this review considered the literature published over the last two decades, from 2003 to 2023 as shown in Figure 1, using key words such as “Non-Destructive Technologies” OR “Non-Destructive Inspection” OR “Non-Destructive Test”, AND “Sustainability Assessment” OR “Sustainable Assessment”. This preliminary search uncovered that only 6 papers specifically addressed the application of all sustainability pillars within the NDI field.

Figure 1. PRISMA SA within NDI

The limited number of relevant papers prompted a deeper investigation into the evolution of sustainability, SA, and NDI concepts over the past 20 years. To accurately trace the trajectory of these fields within academic research, a comprehensive analysis was conducted. This analysis is presented in three key graphs: Figure 2 highlights the growth of sustainability studies, reflecting the increasing academic focus. Figure 3 examines the evolution of sustainability assessments, offering insights into how methodologies and frameworks have been employed over time. Finally, Figure 4 tracks the development of NDI studies, showcasing advancements in technology with the potential to reduce waste and increase efficiency. Together, these graphs provide a holistic view of how these three concepts have evolved within academic research, laying the groundwork for a more integrated framework in future studies.

Figure 2. Sustainable /Sustainability articles 2003-2023

Figure 3. Sustainability assessment OR Sustainable assessment articles 2003- 2023

Figure 4. Non destructive technology OR Non destructive inspection articles 2003- 2023

These graphs reveal significant annual growth rates of 17%, 18%, and 11% for sustainability studies, sustainability assessments, and NDI studies, respectively, highlighting a clear and rising academic interest in these areas. This steady increase reflects a growing recognition of their relevance in addressing contemporary challenges. However, despite this rapid expansion, a stark contrast emerges when examining the intersection of sustainability concepts with NDI technologies. The scarcity of literature that directly integrates these two critical areas underscores a critical deficiency in the existing body of knowledge. This shortfall not only emphasizes the need for more targeted research but also suggests that the potential benefits of

merging sustainability principles with NDI practices remain largely untapped. Addressing this issue is crucial for advancing in both fields and ensuring that technological innovations are fully aligned with broader sustainability goals.

Therefore, a detailed and separate analysis of the different pillars of sustainability as applied to NDI technologies is proposed. To achieve this, a new study will be conducted using the PRISMA methodology, now integrating key concepts such as environmental, economic and social assessments. These approaches will be explained in detail in the following section, providing a comprehensive and specific view of how each pillar contributes to a more complete and accurate sustainability assessment in the context of NDI.

FRAMEWORK

Sustainability assessment models have evolved significantly through ongoing research and practical application. The most robust contemporary models now integrate what are known as the triple bottom of sustainability: the environmental, economic, and social components. However, the literature reveals a variety of methodologies for evaluating each of these components individually [7]. In order to address this issue, a new study was carried out using the PRISMA methodology to identify the most commonly used models, with the aim of defining a more appropriate approach to be applied to NDI topics.

Figure 5. PRISMA Environmental, economic and social pillars for NDI

RESULTS

The results aim to address the research questions state at the beginning of the study: First, what is the state of the practice in assessing the sustainability of these technologies? Second, which methodologies or tools are used to analyse the environmental, economic, and social impacts of their implementation? In response to the first question, the study concludes that sustainability is only partially evaluated in NDI practices. Another key aspect of the results is that they serve as a foundation for achieving the study's objectives: exploring the contribution of sustainability assessment to NDI and describing the technical principles and application of sustainability assessment in different NDI technologies.

The study selected four methodologies for each sustainability pillar: environmental, economic, and social. Table 1 highlights the advantages of applying each methodology to non-destructive inspection; it is important to note that this study is cross-sectoral, considering applications across various industries. It also summarizes the methodologies identified in the literature.

Table 1. Methodologies for environmental, economic and social assessment and advantages in NDI

METHODOLOGY	DEFINITION	ADVANTAGES IN NDI
Environmental Impact Assessment (EIA)	Evaluates potential environmental effects of a project.	Identifies environmental impacts of NDI, ensuring regulatory compliance.
Life Cycle Assessment (LCA)	Assesses environmental impacts throughout a product's life.	Evaluates full environmental footprint of NDI tools, promoting sustainability.
Strategic Environmental Assessment (SEA)	Evaluates environmental effects of policies, plans, and programs.	Integrates NDI methods into broader strategies, aligning with sustainability goals.
Carbon Footprint Analysis	Calculates total greenhouse gases emitted by a project.	Minimizes carbon emissions from NDI, reducing overall carbon footprint.
Cost-Benefit Analysis (CBA)	Compares costs and benefits to determine overall value.	Assesses economic feasibility of NDI technologies.
Economic Impact Analysis (EIA)	Evaluates the economic effect of a project on a specific area.	Analyzes economic impact of NDI adoption on local/regional economies.
Techno-Economic Analysis (TEA)	Combines technical and economic aspects to evaluate viability.	Assesses technical performance and economic feasibility of NDI technologies.
Life Cycle Costing (LCC)	Assesses total cost of ownership over a product's lifecycle.	Understands long-term cost implications of NDI technologies.
Social Impact Assessment (SIA)	Evaluates social consequences of a project, including impacts on communities.	Understands social implications of NDI technology deployment in sensitive environments.
Stakeholder Analysis	Identifies and assesses the influence of key stakeholders.	Identifies stakeholders affected by NDI technologies and addresses their concerns.
Social Sustainability Assessment (SSA)	Evaluates social dimensions of sustainability, including equity and social well-being.	Ensures NDI technologies contribute to social sustainability, enhancing equity and community resilience.
Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA)	Assesses social impacts throughout the lifecycle, focusing on stakeholders across the supply chain.	Evaluates social impacts of NDI technologies across the supply chain, promoting ethical practices.

To defining a tailored framework for integrating sustainability assessment into NDI and address the objective of the study, Table 2 is presented. This table summarizes the advantages of the selected methodologies – Life Cycle Costing (LCC), Life Cycle Assessment (LCA), and Social Life Cycle Assessment (SLCA) – which together provide a holistic approach to evaluating sustainability in the practice of non-destructive inspection (NDI).

Table 2. Main aspects for LCA, LCC and SLCA in NDI

ASPECT	LCA	LCC	SLCA
Comprehensive Scope	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> -Evaluates environmental impacts across lifecycle. - Identifies issues at each stage. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Analyzes total costs throughout lifecycle. - Supports financial decisions. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Assesses social impacts like labor and community conditions. - Promotes social sustainability.
Systematic Approach	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Standardized, ISO-based methodology. - Ensures consistent assessments. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systematic evaluation of lifecycle costs. - Supports cost management. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Structured approach with UNEP/SETAC guidelines. - Aligned with best practices.
Identification of Key Impact Areas	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Identifies environmental ‘hot spots.’ - Targets sustainability improvements. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Pinpoints major cost drivers. - Focuses on reducing expenses. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Highlights social ‘hot spots’ like labor issues. - Enables targeted actions.
Decision Support	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Provides insights for sustainable design and policies. - Helps reduce footprint. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Offers financial insights for decision-making. - Balances cost efficiency and viability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Delivers information for CSR and supply chain management. - Enhances social sustainability.
Comparative Analysis	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compares products/processes based on environmental impacts. - Supports sustainable options. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Facilitates comparison based on lifecycle costs. - Ensures financial sustainability. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Compares options based on social impacts. - Aligns with ethical standards.
Transparency and Credibility	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Transparent methodology enhances credibility. - Builds stakeholder trust. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Promotes transparency in cost assessments. - Ensures reliable data. 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Maintains transparency in social assessments. - Demonstrates social responsibility.

DISCUSSION

In recent scholarly discussions, the importance of integrating a holistic approach to sustainability assessment processes has been underscored, with particular emphasis on moving beyond the traditional three pillars of sustainable development: environmental, economic and social. The literature argues that minimizing negative impacts alone is insufficient; instead, assessments must actively promote actions that contribute positively to the community and ecological sustainability, fostering a future that is viable, pleasant, and secure [46]. This systems approach aims to achieve net sustainability gains by enhancing system health and resilience over the long term, reflecting advanced thinking in the field.

Moreover, the current models of mitigation, which focus heavily on the avoidance and minimization of impacts, have proven ineffective. This inadequacy calls for a re-evaluation of the existing mitigation hierarchy, advocating for the prioritization of 'enhancement' at the top of the hierarchy [47].

Building on the aforementioned points, this study conducted a comprehensive analysis of the methodologies employed within each pillar of sustainability into NDI. This analysis serves as the foundation for adopting a more holistic perspective. Additionally, the study is guided by a set of specific rules, outlined below, to offer a well-rounded solution to the challenges identified [48]:

- a) Net Gains: Every trade-off considered must result in net sustainability gains, particularly over the long term. This criterion ensures that any compromise made ultimately enhances overall sustainability.
- b) Burden of Argument: The responsibility to justify any proposed trade-off lies with its proponent. This principle demands a rigorous demonstration of why the trade-off is necessary and beneficial.
- c) Avoidance of Significant Adverse Effects: No trade-off that results in significant adverse effects is acceptable unless it is demonstrated that all other alternatives are worse. This guideline safeguards against detrimental compromises that could undermine sustainability goals.
- d) Protection of the Future: Shifting significant adverse impacts from the present to the future cannot be justified unless it is clear that all other alternatives are less favourable. This rule is crucial in ensuring that sustainability efforts do not merely defer problems to future generations.
- e) Explicit Justification: Every trade-off must be explicitly justified, with a detailed, context-specific explanation of priorities and sustainability decision criteria. This transparency is vital for accountability and trust in the decision-making process.
- f) Open Process: Stakeholders must be actively involved in the trade-off decision-making process through open and effective participatory methods. This inclusion ensures that diverse perspectives are considered, and that decisions are made transparently and democratically.

CONCLUSION

This study addresses the integration of SA and NDI with the goal of understanding and improving the practice of these technologies through a holistic approach that considers environmental, economic, and social impacts. Through a systematic review using the PRISMA methodology, two key questions were identified: the current state of practice in assessing the sustainability of NDI technologies, and the methodologies/tools used to analyze the impacts of their implementation.

Key Conclusions

1. **Lack of Comprehensive SA:** While the literature shows growing interest in sustainability and NDI technologies, there is a significant gap in the comprehensive evaluation of sustainability in this field. Current assessments tend to focus on individual aspects, mainly environmental impact, without deeply analyzing how these aspects interact with economic viability and social consequences. This fragmented view risks leading to incomplete or misleading assessments that could undermine decision-making and policy development.
2. **Need for Integrated Approaches:** To address this deficiency, the study proposes a novel framework that integrates methodologies such as LCA, LCC, and SLCA into NDI practice. This approach promises a more holistic application of sustainability principles, facilitating their effective incorporation into the analysis of future NDI projects.
3. **Development of an Evaluation Framework:** A tailored evaluation framework was developed, combining LCA, LCC, and SLCA, providing a systematic methodology for assessing sustainability in NDI. This framework enables the identification of key impact areas within each of the sustainability pillars, supporting informed decision-making and promoting sustainable practices in non-destructive inspection.
4. **Recommendations for Future Research:** The study emphasizes the importance of conducting further research that effectively integrates sustainability principles into NDI practices, highlighting the need to address the interconnections between sustainability pillars to achieve a more complete and accurate assessment.

Implications

The study establishes that integrating sustainability assessment into NDI is crucial for advancing both technological practices and broader sustainability goals. By developing a framework that holistically considers environmental, economic, and social impacts, it lays the groundwork for a more robust and sustainable analysis of NDI technologies, which is essential for their responsible implementation across various industries.

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NOMENCLATURE

Acronyms/Abbreviations

ABBREVIATION	MEANING
CBA	Cost-Benefit Analysis
EIA	Environmental Impact Assessment
EIA	Economic Impact Analysis
LCA	Life Cycle Assessment
LCC	Life Cycle Costing
NDI	Non- Destructive Inspection
PRISMA	Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses
SA	sustainability assessment
SEA	Strategic Environmental Assessment
SIA	Social Impact Assessment
SLCA	Social Life Cycle Assessment
SSA	Social Sustainability Assessment
TEA	Techno-Economic Analysis

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